

EARTH SCIENCES

PERSONALIZED SOLUTIONS IN THE PACKAGING BUSINESS

Nikitenko O.

master's degree,

National Technical University «Kharkiv Polytechnic Institute»

Abstract

This article examines personalized solutions in the packaging business and their impact on consumer behavior and brand reinforcement. The core principles of personalization as a marketing tool, its role in modern branding strategies, and theoretical aspects related to establishing an emotional connection with consumers are analyzed. Special attention is given to technological innovations such as digital and 3D printing, augmented reality, and automation, which allow packaging to be tailored to individual preferences. Practical examples of successful use of personalized packaging (PP) by companies are provided.

Keywords: personalized packaging (PP), branding, consumer behavior, technology, loyalty, custom design, marketing.

Introduction

Personalized packaging (PP) is a prevailing trend in marketing and branding, fueled by rising competitiveness and shifting consumer tastes. This subject is important because contemporary customers anticipate distinctive and unforgettable products, while companies aim to establish an emotional connection with consumers using individually designed packaging. Currently, packaging is more than just providing protection and information. It also plays a crucial role in shaping brand image and impacting consumer actions.

In today's market, where consumers have many options with similar features, PP helps brands differentiate and solidify their positions. Tailored packaging that catches the eye and gives a feeling of being special helps in forming stronger and more enduring connections with customers. In the era of digitalization, as technology allows for mass personalization, the importance of customized strategies is increasing, becoming essential in the competition for customer engagement and commitment. The goal of this research is to explore the impact of PP on consumer behavior and branding.

Main part. Defining the personalized approach and impact of custom design on consumer behavior

Personalization in marketing is about customizing product offerings for individual consumers or specific audiences, standing out and building stronger customer connections. Personalization, as opposed to mass strategies, seeks to cater to individual tastes, enriching the positive encounter with the brand. Considering the audience's demographic, behavioral, and psychological traits, this approach offers consumers a feeling of individuality and intimacy [1]. Increased loyalty, increased repeat purchases, and emotional attachment to the brand are some of the main benefits, as consumers believe that their needs and interests are recognized.

Initially, packaging performed only utilitarian functions, protecting and storing products. However, with the development of marketing, its significance has greatly expanded. Now, it serves as a means of visual communication, helping brands stand out and immediately attract consumer attention. The shift from purely

functional packaging to one that holds emotional meaning reflects modern consumer preferences for quality combined with meaningful interaction with a product.

Custom design has a significant impact on the perception of the brand, increasing its attractiveness and uniqueness in the eyes of consumers PP. Custom design elements in packaging make consumers feel that a product has been specially created for them, strengthening the sense of special attention from the brand. This individual approach fosters trust and positive brand perception, as consumers view the brand as one that understands and values their personal preferences and needs. Such a focus on personalization helps brands differentiate themselves from competitors and create stronger associations with their products, leading to a sustainable image and a higher likelihood of consumer choice.

An important role in the formation and strengthening of brand loyalty is played by PP. When consumers see that a brand makes an effort to create a unique product tailored to their preferences, they feel valued and respected, which promotes deeper engagement with the brand. Loyalty grows due to the positive experience associated with the product: unique packaging becomes a symbol of an individualized approach, strengthening attachment to the brand and encouraging repeat purchases [2]. Additionally, personalized elements can remind consumers of their positive interactions with the brand, fostering a lasting sense of satisfaction and commitment, as consumers see their interests and values reflected in the brand.

Numerous studies confirm that PP affects consumer behavior, increasing satisfaction and strengthening brand connection. For instance, in 2023, McKinsey and NIQ conducted a study that highlighted the significant influence of personalization and eco-friendliness in packaging on consumer preferences. According to the study, 71% of consumers expect personalized interactions from brands and are disappointed when companies do not provide this experience. Personalization has been proven to boost loyalty and engagement, as clients prefer companies that consider their preferences and offer individual recommendations and offers. Additionally, the study found that 92% of consumers prefer eco-

friendly products, especially those with environmental labels on the packaging [3]. Thus, NIQ and McKinsey note that eco-friendliness has become an important factor in increasing brand confidence, especially among

the younger generation, sensitive to environmental problems.

Moreover, according to a McKinsey & Co report, personalization can increase profit even for companies that lack direct customer access, such as those in the consumer goods sector (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Growth of companies using personalization [4]

It is noted that companies with the highest profit growth rates prioritized personalization far more often than those with lower growth rates. The study shows that even minor changes aimed at enhancing customer interaction create a competitive advantage, which grows as development continues. These findings underscore the importance of personalization and eco-friendliness for building an emotional connection with consumers and fostering loyalty, which is particularly relevant given the rising expectations for socially responsible brand behavior.

Personalized solutions in branding

Packaging plays a crucial role in creating brand identity, acting as a powerful tool for visual and emotional communication. Being the first physical contact of the consumer with the product, the packaging sets the tone for interaction with the brand and creates an initial impression of its values, style, and character. The use of PP helps the brand to show its unique features and convey its philosophy, strengthening the perception of the brand as special and caring for consumers. It is important to note that packaging also serves as a communication channel: Through the choice of colors, textures and materials, brands convey their principles and values, such as environmental friendliness, innovation or premium. In this way, packaging becomes a part

of the overall history of the brand and a way to communicate with the audience, strengthening its identity and increasing awareness.

Creating a PP strategy requires a careful approach to ensure that the design, materials, and personalization tactics meet the expectations of different target groups. First of all, brands analyze the demographic and behavioral characteristics of their audience in order to understand which elements are most important for each of the groups. For example, environmentally conscious consumers will appreciate packaging made of recycled materials, and a young audience focused on digital technologies may be interested in interactive elements. When developing personalized solutions, brands pay special attention to the choice of colors, fonts and graphic elements so that they accurately convey the image of the brand and reflect its values. In addition, the use of various materials and packaging forms allows you to adapt offers to specific markets or festive events, making the product especially attractive and memorable. Therefore, in the modern packaging business, personalization covers a wide range of solutions aimed at attracting and retaining consumers. Table 1 presents the main types of PP.

Table 1.

Types of PP [5]		
Type of PP	Description	Advantages
Personal inscriptions	Putting a name, greeting, or personal message on the packaging enhances the emotional connection with the product.	Increases loyalty and creates a sense of uniqueness, making the product meaningful to the consumer.
Adapting the design to the audience	Changing colors, shapes and graphic elements depending on the characteristics of the target audience or the season.	Attracts target groups and creates relevance, enhancing the sense of belonging to the brand.
Limited edition and collectible packages	Unique designs for limited edition, which increases interest in the product and its value to collectors.	It stimulates interest and increases the value of the product due to its limitations and exclusivity.
Interactive elements	QR codes, augmented reality and other digital technologies that provide access to additional information or content.	Improves the user experience through interactive interaction and strengthens the connection with the brand.
Eco-friendly materials	The use of recycled, biodegradable or renewable materials to maintain the sustainability and environmental friendliness of the brand.	It attracts environmentally conscious consumers, improves brand perception and emphasizes its responsibility.
Unique shapes and textures	Creating original shapes and textures that emphasize the character of the product and add aesthetic value.	Enhances the perception of the premium and uniqueness of the product, improving its visual appeal on the shelf.

According to the author, these types of PP provide brands with flexibility and adaptability in building deeper relationships with consumers. Thanks to a variety of solutions, companies can not only meet individual preferences but also enhance the emotional perception of their products. Thus, PP becomes a powerful tool in a competitive environment, increasing brand value in the eyes of consumers and fostering their loyalty and readiness for repeat purchases.

Many brands have already successfully implemented personalized solutions in their packaging, demonstrating flexibility and creativity in their approach to personalization. For example, **Coca-Cola** launched the «Share a Coke» campaign, offering bottles with names, which not only drew attention to the product but also formed an emotional connection with consumers. The campaign was so successful that the brand expanded it by adding popular phrases and expressions to the bottles, enhancing personalization [6].

Another example is **M&M**, which allowed customers to add personalized inscriptions on candies and choose individual color combinations for packaging, making them especially attractive for gifts and special occasions. This approach made the product more emotionally significant and contributed to sales growth [7]. These examples illustrate that PP solutions can effectively boost brand recognition, foster emotional attachment, and increase audience loyalty.

Technological innovations in PP

Technological innovations in the packaging industry enable brands to create unique personalized solutions that meet modern consumers' demands for individuality and sustainability. In recent years, PP has become possible through several advancements, including digital technologies, automation, and eco-friendly materials, allowing brands to engage more deeply with customers and maintain their interest.

Intelligent data analysis has become an important tool for understanding consumer behavior. With large data sets, companies can analyze customer

preferences, behaviors, and purchase histories to create individualized offers based on these insights. This enhances loyalty and helps establish strong connections between the brand and the consumer.

Various **modern printing technologies** play a crucial role in PP, allowing for unique designs with lower costs and at minimal order quantities. Unlike traditional printing, digital printing and variable data printing enable the creation of unique elements on each product unit, giving brands the ability to tailor packaging to specific events or customer preferences. **Augmented reality and Quick Response codes** bridge the physical and digital worlds, providing consumers with an opportunity to interact with products on a new level. Scanning codes on packaging gives access to interactive and personalized content, making each product unique. Interactive elements such as hidden messages and pull-out tabs also offer deeper interaction with the packaging, making the unboxing process part of the overall product experience.

3D printing allows for the creation of custom shapes and complex design elements, making packaging unique and memorable. This opens up new opportunities for creating a distinctive brand style and packaging design that adds aesthetic and emotional value to the product [8]. Personalized labels and stickers also play a significant role, as they allow for the addition of unique elements to the packaging, making the product more valuable and individual. **Blockchain** ensures supply chain transparency, which is especially important for conscious consumers seeking sustainability and transparency. Brands can use this technology to share information about the product's origin and production processes, enhancing consumer trust and allowing them to make informed choices.

Technological innovations in PP allow brands to offer customers unique and meaningful solutions tailored to their expectations and values. Digital technologies, automation, and eco-friendly materials provide a

high degree of personalization while supporting environmental responsibility. Collectively, these advancements make PP an essential element of branding that strengthens loyalty and enhances the positive perception of the brand in the eyes of consumers. Using such technologies not only meets modern consumer expectations but also increases brand loyalty. Modern solutions make packaging interactive and emotionally significant, creating memorable impressions that resonate with audiences and foster long-term brand relationships.

Conclusion

The practice of PP holds a strong place in the marketing strategies of leading brands, driven by growing consumer expectations for unique, meaningful, and environmentally friendly products. Packaging has ceased to be just a protective shell and has become a powerful communication channel that helps build and strengthen the connection between the brand and its customers. In a highly competitive environment with a wide range of products available, PP elements not only distinguish the brand but also enhance its appeal.

Technological advances such as 3D printing, intelligent data analytics, and augmented reality enable brands to create flexible and scalable personalized solutions capable of meeting a wide range of consumer preferences. These innovations make PP accessible to the mass market, helping companies meet the demand for individualized and sustainable solutions. Recent research confirms that PP increases consumer loyalty and satisfaction, encouraging repeat purchases and strengthening brand commitment. Thus, PP becomes an

essential tool for creating competitive advantages and long-term relationships with consumers.

References

1. Ahmed A. Customer Relationship Management: Best Practices for Business Managers // *Journal for Business Research Review*. 2024. Vol. 2. №. 1. P. 13-25.
2. Pshychenko D. Study of artificial intelligence models for big data analysis in project management // *International Journal of Humanities and Natural Sciences*. 2024. Vol. 8-3. № 95. P. 180-185.
3. Doan D., Poirier A. Industry Implications of Evolving Consumer Behaviour. 2023.
4. The value of getting personalization right – or wrong – is multiplying / McKinsey // URL: <https://www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/growth-marketing-and-sales/our-insights/the-value-of-getting-personalization-right-or-wrong-is-multiplying#/> (date of application 25.10.2024).
5. Fomicheva E. Modeling the efficiency of marketing budget allocation in multichannel promotion environments // *Vestnik nauki*. 2024. Vol. 1. № 10. P. 14-21.
6. Visser M., Kloos M. Customer acquisition: digital brand communications // *Digital Marketing Fundamentals*. – Routledge. 2021. P. 170-221.
7. Singh J., Shukla P. Brand Management: Principles and Applications for Effective Branding. – Kogan Page Publishers. 2024.
8. Merlo A. Developing business intelligence solutions for consumer packaged goods industry in a start-up environment. 2023.